

DESIGNING COMPOSITES FOR ENERGY ABSORPTION UNDER TENSILE LOADING

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SUMMARY: Novel composites have been developed possessing exceptionally high capacity for energy absorption. This was accomplished by arranging the geometry of the reinforcement in such a way that the composite hardens over large strains (~100%) following the onset of damage, leading to damage delocalization. Composites have been made using steel chains and fiber tows braided or knitted into configurations possessing large strain capacity, consolidated with polymeric or metallic matrices. The energy absorbed per unit volume by the first generation of these composites varies between 15 and 60 MJ/m³, which is already very favourable compared to other candidate materials for energy absorption. The energy absorbed per unit mass ranges from about 8-13 J/g for chain composites to more than 20 J/g for fibre-reinforced composites. These are also very attractive values. By optimizing the reinforcement geometry and the matrix properties, both the chain and textile composites can be tailored to have energy absorption still several times higher.

INTRODUCTION

Many energy absorption problems involve loads that are tensile, for example, casings designed to contain bursting rotors, turbines, or flywheels; backing plates in armour systems; and containers subject to internal explosions. Here some results are shown for a new class of composites with unusually high energy absorption capacity under tensile loading.

The new composites incorporate mechanisms for ensuring that damage is broadly distributed throughout the body of a specimen or structure before the instability associated with ultimate failure sets in. Damage delocalization is promoted by incorporating so-called lock-up mechanisms, in which components of the reinforcement are arrested by physical contact with one another after displacing through the matrix. The extent of the displacement allowed before the lock-up of two elements of the reinforcement determines the global strain up to which damage will be delocalized, denoted ϵ_c . The total energy absorbed per unit volume is bounded from below by the product of ϵ_c and the magnitude of the global stress required for reinforcement displacement, σ_d .

Both σ_d and ϵ_c can be varied over quite wide ranges by selecting materials and the geometry of the reinforcement, so that composites can be designed, for example, to avoid large stresses during energy absorption; or for maximum total energy absorption without constraint on the stress level. The levels of total energy absorbed per unit volume or per unit mass by members of the new class of composites are potentially very high.

COMPOSITES OF CHAINS

Composites of chains in epoxy matrices in which the links are initially in a contracted configuration (Fig. 1) fail with damage spread over the whole stressed volume and absorb unusually large energy per unit volume during failure. The underlying phenomena were first discussed in [1] and have now been analyzed quantitatively by analytical and computational methods [2,3]. Damage begins with extensive matrix cracking. Successive chain links slide towards contact with one another, crushing resin trapped between them in a state of near hydrostatic compression. The displacement of links through the resin absorbs most of the energy expended en route to ultimate failure. When two links come into direct contact, they are said to lock up: the material hardens locally, resisting further local displacement and triggering the displacement of links elsewhere in the same chain. Only when all links in a chain are in direct contact with their neighbors does the chain begin to fail by plastic deformation of the links followed by rupture of the weakest among them.

Fig. 1: Contracted chain configuration viewed through a transparent epoxy matrix.

Estimates Based on Simple Models

A typical stress-strain curve is shown in Fig. 2. During link displacement, the applied engineering stress is approximately constant in most chain/polymer composites (strain less than 0.5 in Fig. 2). Its magnitude can be estimated by modeling the matrix as a rigid/perfectly plastic medium through which the links must move. Stress transfer into the links from the matrix during the displacement can be partitioned conveniently into several contributions. 1) Hydrostatic compression in the resin trapped between two links as they approach one another exerts pressure over the inner surface of the crown of each link (the curved end). 2) Shear tractions develop over the crown of a link as it slides through the matrix. 3) Tensile tractions act on the outer surface of the crown where the matrix is being pulled apart between the crowns of abutting links, at least until the matrix fails (e.g., along line A-A in Fig. 1). 4) Shear stresses act over the legs (the straight portions) as the links slide through the matrix.

The sum of the four contributions, when resolved in the direction of the motion of the links, must be balanced by tension in the legs, which takes its maximum value, $\sigma_{\max}^{(leg)}$, at the centre of the legs; and all four are proportional to the matrix shear flow stress, σ_{my} , the constants of proportionality depending on the link geometry. Summarizing the results of finite element calculations [2]

$$\sigma_{\max}^{(leg)} = \beta \sigma_{my} \quad (1)$$

$$\beta \equiv \frac{2}{\pi} (C_1 + C_2 + 3.664 C_3) \left(1 + \frac{R}{r} \right) - \left(\frac{C_1 - C_2}{2} \right) + C_4 \frac{H}{r}$$

where r is the radius of the wire in the link, R is the inner radius of the crown segment, and H is the length of the leg segment; and C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 are dimensionless constants of proportionality corresponding in order to the four contributions listed above. The constants C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 were evaluated in [2]. Equation (1) is restricted to links consisting of semi-toroidal crowns connected by cylindrical legs, which is the standard geometry of commercially available chains. For perfectly bonded link/matrix interfaces, the proportionality factor β reduces to the even simpler result

$$\beta = 2.37 + 3.32 \frac{R}{r} + 0.5 \frac{H}{r} \quad (2)$$

and for unbonded, frictionless interfaces to

$$\beta = 0.36 + 1.69 \frac{R}{r} \quad (3)$$

If the matrix is relatively compliant, then Eq. (1) multiplied by the area fraction occupied by the legs of the links on a plane through their centres (e.g., the plane A-A in Fig. 1) should be approximately equal to the composite stress during link displacement, σ_d . This is shown in Fig. 2 by the line marked " $\sigma_r = \beta \sigma_{my}$ ". It coincides with the measured plateau stress.

A transition from delocalized to localized failure should occur if $\sigma_{\max}^{(leg)}$ exceeds the strength of the chain material, σ_{ch} , during link displacement through the matrix. This was not the case in the test of Fig. 2. However, when the composite stress divided by the area fraction of the links, which is denoted σ_r , exceeds σ_{ch} following link lockup, the chains must fail. This condition is indicated by the line marked " $\sigma_r = \sigma_{ch}$ " in Fig. 2, which is somewhat above the measured peak stress. The discrepancy is due to slightly unequal loading among the chains.

The estimates of the plateau stress and the failure stress based on Eq. (1) are very useful as design guides.

Fig. 2: Measured stress-strain curve for a chain/polycarbonate composite.

Energy Absorption Values – Current and Ideal

The energy absorption per unit volume, W , is compared in Figure 3 for the chain composites and other energy-absorbing materials, including cold drawing polymers, monolithic alloys, and some recently developed braided composite tubes [4]. The cold drawing polymers are typified by polycarbonate, which sustains relatively low loads but can achieve strains of several hundred percent. The energy absorption of alloys is estimated as the area under typical tensile stress-strain curves prior to the formation of any necking instability. The energy absorption data are plotted in Fig. 3 against strength. The highest value of energy absorption for the chains composites was approximately 60 MJ/m^3 in a chain/polycarbonate composite (datum “8” in Fig. 3).

Barring idealized chain composites to be discussed below, monolithic alloys and cold-drawing polymers possess the highest values of W , but other aspects of behaviour must also be considered. The degree of global plasticity attained in both alloys and polymers is quite sensitive to the presence of notches or other stress concentrators, which might be created by the geometry of the part design or damage. Localized failure will occur in alloys if the notch size exceeds a few mm at most [5]. Polycarbonate, a typical cold-drawing polymer, is even more sensitive to notches. The presence of a sub-millimeter nick in the side of a polycarbonate sheet will lead to localized failure and pre-empt cold drawing [1]. Furthermore, cold drawing of polymers is also very rate sensitive, with failure at even moderately elevated strain rates reverting to brittle behaviour. The localization/delocalization transition in chain composites will be much less sensitive to notches, because the chains do not communicate stress concentrations effectively. They are mechanically decoupled early in the failure process. Delocalization in the chain composites is also relatively insensitive to strain rate, a point that will be demonstrated elsewhere.

The values of W found for the chain composites are similar to those obtained for the braided composite tubes developed by Harte and Fleck [4]. Tubes braided at angles between 23° and 55° to the tube axis exhibit delocalized failure under axial tension, with a necking and drawing mechanism analogous to a cold drawing polymer. The failure involves shearing and scissoring of cross-braided tows, with lockup caused by rotation of the fibers and tows into hard contact with one another. The peak axial stress is typically ~ 30 MPa and the total energy absorbed per unit volume can reach ~ 30 MJ/m³, figures somewhat below the chain composites. However, the chain composites have further significant advantages. They do not need to be tubular; and their stiffness, strength, and energy absorbing capacity can be made even higher by a combination of material selection and redesign of the link geometry.

Fig. 3: The energy absorption, W , for chain composites that have already been tested (numbered data points), hypothetical, optimal chain composites, and other groups of materials. Typical scatter is represented by elliptical domains, following the style of the materials selection charts of Ashby [6]. The energy data are plotted against composite or material strength.

The appropriate figure of merit for applications demanding high energy absorption but low weight is the energy absorbed per unit volume or specific energy absorption, $W_s = W/\rho_c$, with ρ_c the composite density. This is plotted in Fig. 4 against the specific strength, $\sigma_s = \sigma_c/\rho_c$. Here the chain composites stand up very well against monolithic alloys and are not far from the braided tubes. Again the highest value for the chain composites, 14 J/g, is for a chain/polycarbonate composite. Cold drawing polymers have the highest specific energy absorption, but even these levels can be equaled for optimized chain composites.

The energy absorption of the chain composites will be maximized by 1) packing the chains as closely as possible; 2) using the strongest possible chain material, thus maximizing the allowable stress, σ_d , during link displacement; 3) choosing a matrix with a flow stress, σ_{my} , for which the product $\beta\sigma_{my}$ is as great as possible without exceeding the chain strength, σ_{ch} ; and

4) choosing a link geometry that maximizes the strain before lockup, ϵ_c . Commercial chains, such as those used in tests to date, do not have very high ultimate strength (< 500 MPa), because relatively ductile alloys must be used for safety. A chain must not break before showing visible signs of plastic strain. However, this is unnecessary in the chain composites, in which high strength steel ($\sigma_{ch} \sim 1$ GPa) could be used without significant loss of composite ductility. By using longer links, the lockup strain, ϵ_c , can be raised to 0.6, somewhat higher than the values (≤ 0.5) for the chains used to date. Finally, the flow stress of the matrix material, σ_{my} , must be raised above current levels (~ 100 MPa for epoxy in compression) to raise the displacement stress, σ_d , to the maximum allowable for stronger links. With all these modifications and closely packed chains of the conventional racetrack shape, the energy absorbed per unit volume during link displacement alone can be raised to approximately 160 MJ/m^3 . This value has been indicated in Fig. 3 as a range attainable for “ideal” chain composites. It is a very attractive prospect.

Fig. 4: The specific energy absorption, W_s , for chain composites (numbered data points), hypothetical, optimal chain composites, and other groups of materials, plotted against specific strength.

The specific energy absorption attainable for carbon steel chain composites with the same steps towards optimization is approximately 40 J/g . This is indicated in Fig. 4 by the “ideal” chain composite. It is again a very attractive goal.

CONTINUOUS FIBER COMPOSITES

A lockup mechanism analogous to that in the chain composites can be achieved with continuous fiber reinforcement by novel arrangements of loops formed by braiding or knitting. In the textile process, interpenetrating loops are formed, which in analogy to the contracted configuration of links depicted in Fig. 1, are not in intimate contact until they have displaced towards one another after an applied load has created extensive matrix damage. Loops

formed by braiding and knitting are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: (a) Braided reinforcement configuration, formed on a series of rods to control loop separation. The tows have been spread into a loose arrangement to allow their interlacing pattern to be seen more easily. In the finished composite, they are tightly packed in the horizontal direction in the figure, but retain their elongation in the vertical direction (the intended direction of loading). (b) Schematic of weft knit in which loops have been separated so as not to be initially in intimate contact by knitting onto rods similar to those in (a) (not depicted). In (b), the intended loading direction is horizontal.

Composites can be formed with the braided or knitted reinforcements by infiltrating with epoxy resin. Since there is no limit to the initial overlap of loops (the fraction of a loop's length by which interpenetrating loops are set apart on the positioning rods) in either design, there is no limit to the lockup strain, e_c . Braided composites fabricated to date have exhibited delocalized failure with ultimate strains to failure of 300% or more. The maximum loads during failure in braided composites are ~ 30 MPa for the tow packing densities achieved so far. Figure 6 shows a typical stress-strain record for a braided composite achieving the somewhat lower maximum stress of 18 MPa and a plateau stress, $\sigma_d \approx 10$ MPa, but extending to a strain exceeding 400%. The energy absorbed per unit volume in this test was approximately 30 MJ/m^3 and the specific energy absorbed approximately 24 J/g. With some fairly obvious improvements in the braiding technique to achieve higher fiber packing densities and some modifications to the matrix to avoid premature loss of matrix material during loop displacement, the plateau stress could be raised much higher. Quite interesting combinations of strain to failure, peak stress, and energy absorption could then be achieved. The braided composites will clearly rival the best chain composites and outstrip other classes of material.

Fig. 6: Stress-strain plot for braided specimen.

Fig. 7 shows a knitted specimen before and after testing. The fabric is wrapped with a small amount of yarn to inhibit the loss of matrix during large sliding displacements. The wrapped fibers are only partly effective in this. A better method, not yet pursued, would be to toughen the matrix by incorporating chopped fibers in it, for example. Because of premature loss of resin, the stress during the initial stages of loop displacement is smaller than in the chain or braided composites. Figure 8 shows a case in which the initial stresses are especially low (they are > 10 MPa in other cases, depending on the aspect ratios and initial overlap of the loops), but it illustrates another characteristic peculiar to the knitted structure. As the knitted loops (such as those in Fig. 5b) are drawn tight during loop displacement, they are pulled against one another laterally in an action similar to tightening a knot, resulting in increasing and ultimately very strong frictional forces between them. (The distinction between knitted loops and braided loops or chain links is in the topology of the interlacing of the loops. The braided loops and chain links approach one another after sliding displacement with the curved ends – e.g., the crowns of the chain links – orthogonal to one another and perhaps without lateral contact. Interpenetrating knitted loops approach one another obliquely with a tightening action.) Thus the knitted composites tend to exhibit gradual hardening during the loop displacement phase. The stress in the example of Fig. 8 rises by a factor of about three before tow rupture leads to specimen failure. In Fig. 8, the strain to failure is nearly 300%. If the initial overlap of the knitted loops is reduced, the stress during sliding displacement tends to rise (to approximately 20 MPa in cases tested to date), while the strain to ultimate failure decreases (to ~ 100 % in the cases of highest sliding stress). The energy absorbed per unit volume in knitted composites made to date ranges up to about 25 MJ/m^3 and the specific energy absorbed is about 18 J/g . Substantial improvement could be achieved by using a matrix, e.g., one reinforced by chopped fibers, that was not as easily ejected during loop displacement. Resin is more easily lost from the knitted loops than from braided loops or chain links, because it is not trapped as effectively in pockets in which large hydrostatic compression can develop.

a)

b)

Fig. 7: (a) A knitted Kevlar/epoxy composite as fabricated. (b) Tested composite showing distributed damage.

Fig. 8: Stress-strain data for a composite of knitted Kevlar tows impregnated with student-friendly Epofix epoxy resin.

SUMMARY REMARKS

By regarding the geometry of its reinforcement as a design variable, unusual failure mechanisms can be built into a composite, leading to damage delocalization and exceptionally high values of energy absorption. Values of energy absorbed per unit volume and per unit

mass have been demonstrated that exceed those available from other current candidates for energy absorbing applications. Much higher values could be achieved in the next generation of all classes of these composites, according to estimates made with models of the damage processes.

The composites demonstrated here have been made with common constituents and by processes that appear amenable to automation and cheap mass production.

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